

Synopsis for M.Phil (Islamic Culture)

The Life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه

Correction of the Fallacies in the Encyclopedia of Islam
in the entry by W. Montgomery Watt on the life of Abu Bakr
(Published by Brill, Leiden, Holland)

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Introduction

Orientalists have always regarded Islamic history as an important aspect of their study. The perspective of the earliest orientalists about different personalities and events in the Islamic history was more prejudicial than objective in comparison to the modern orientalists, who try to sound more scientific but due to lack of understanding of the Arabic and reliance on weak narrations have made it impossible for them to show a true and accurate depiction of the Islamic history. The prejudice is sometimes also based on the deliberate rejection of reliable historical resources.

Such articles and researches of the orientalists that demand serious attention in terms of correction are compiled in *The Encyclopedia of Islam*, published by Brill (in Leiden, Holland) under the patronage of the international union of academies, which has attracted students and scholars alike as reference material for over a century now. It has three different editions, the first one being printed between 1913 and 1936 which gave access to 9000 articles, in three different languages – English, French and German.

Need and Importance

The entry by an orientalist W. Montgomery Watt (Watt) pertaining to the life of the first caliph Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه in the Encyclopedia of Islam was subject to the same prejudice and criticism. His services to Islam and the last prophet for the sake of Allah are taken up in a selective way or kept very brief, in result the author in the article has either left his important services or has very doubtfully kept them under investigation as he could not understand the actions of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه due to immeasurable love for the Prophet Muhammad upon whom be peace.

Abu Bakr Al – Siddique's رضى الله عنه reference has been made in several different places including the entry of Mecca and Muhammad but has been taken into account in the special heading of Abu Bakr, the first caliph with the following sub-headings clearly not giving its due importance and detail,

- i. Name, family, and early life,
- ii. From his conversion to the death of Muhammad (upon whom be peace),
- iii. His caliphate.

Since the said encyclopedia is very famous amongst the scholarly circles of East and West due to its cultured language and heritage, therefore, it becomes really important to rectify the errors and propose corrections and editions based on the authentic Islamic sources and provide an

alternative scholarly work in comparison to put an end to the biased approach of the orientalist about the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique raḍiy Allāhu ‘anhu.

Cause for the selection of the topic

There have been several types of research taking place about the works taken by William Montgomery Watt. There is a complete PhD that has been concluded on the life of the said orientalist, however, the said topic had remained untouched, therefore, it became one of the primary reasons to explore it and bring its reality to the face of the public.

Literature Review

A lot of biographies, scholarly articles and research around the world have been conducted by the orientalist on the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه. To name a few,

- i. N. Abbott, Aishah the beloved of Mohammed, Chicago, 1942,
- ii. W. Montgomery Watt, Muhammad at Mecca, Oxford, 1953,
- iii. C. Becker, The Expansion of the Saracens, Cambridge Medieval History, (1912),
- iv. Walker, Adam, Abu Bakr al-Siddiq, in Muhammad in History, Thought, and Culture: An Encyclopedia of the Prophet of God (2 vols.), Edited by C. Fitzpatrick and A. Walker, Santa Barbara, ABC-CLIO, 2014,
- v. Wilferd Madelung (15 October 1998), The Succession to Muhammad: A Study of the Early Caliphate, Cambridge University Press, ISBN 978-0-52-164696-3

But these researches and others only contributed to the primary entry of Watt in the encyclopedia.

Scholars of the Islamic world have taken up this work of defending the life of the beloved of the Prophet, Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه. Some countered the orientalist’s narrative while others worked independently on the said topic, to name a few,

- i. Ayoub, Mahmoud. The Crisis of Muslim History: Religion and Politics in Early Islam. Oxford: Oneworld, 2003.

It is a brief yet scholarly approach to the historical timeline of politics in early Islam dealing with Khilafat e Rashidah.

- ii. El-Hibri, Tayeb. Parable and Politics in Early Islamic History: The Rashidun Caliphs. New York: Columbia University Press, 2010.

It is an essential read for anyone who would like an in-depth analysis of the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه, unlike said orientalist encyclopedia.

- iii. Renard, John. “Abu Bakr in Tradition and Early Hagiography.” In *Tales of God’s Friends: Islamic Hagiography in Translation*. Edited by John Renard, 15–29. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2009.

A really insightful work on Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه offering the translation and contextualization from the writings of Abu Nasr al-Sarraj, Abu Nu’aym al-Asbahani (also transliterated as al-Asfahani), and Hujwiri as well as from the Hadith related to the accounts on Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه.

But none has taken up the entry by Watt from the said encyclopedia related to the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه, though two works of the same nature on the Holy Quran and the Life of the Prophet Muhammad upon whom be peace have been conducted and published in the recent years which are as follows,

- i. Abu Zayd, Ahmed. *THE LIFE OF THE PROPHET, Correction of the Fallacies in the Encyclopedia of Islam* (Published By Brill, Leiden, Holland), Islamic Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 2003.

The author has tried to use the primary sources as well as the ‘Sirah’ writings and also the explanations and the interpretations of the historical sources to put across the actual and authentic narrative to the audience about the Life of the Prophet Muhammad upon whom be peace. He has tried to be objective and avoid prejudice and injurious statements as he put it.

- ii. Aziz, Farhat. *انسائیکلو پیڈیا آف اسلام (لائبڈن) میں قرآن کے مقالے کا ناقدانہ جائزہ*, University of Punjab, Lahore, 2010.

The study was conducted in Pakistan in the Urdu language. The main objectives were to deal with the pieces of evidence put forward by the orientalists with respect to the divine book in the light of Science of Narration, علم الرجال و جرح و تعديل, (*ilmur Rijal& jarrah wa tadeel*). Furthermore, the study was to analyze the view of the orientalists in the light of the explanation of the Quran through Hadith, تفسير القرآن بالحديث and a few other aspects.

No specific study has been conducted to formally analyze the entry of Watt in *The Encyclopedia of Islam* published by Brill (Leiden, Holland) about Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه.

Limitations of the topic

The biggest limitation for the examination and correction of the fallacies in the topic was the death of the author himself, otherwise, it would have been the best option to authenticate why would he ignored the open facts available.

Hypothesis

The author has made biased remarks about the personality of the first caliph Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه due to negligence and the lack of understanding of the primary sources in Islam, in an encyclopedia that is written in the times when organic intellectuals were working in/about the east in the favor of their western masters.

Research questions

How the image of the east, Islam, and the first caliph had been affected due to the biased approach of Orientalism?

Objectives of the research

- To clarify the doubts about the life of the Abu Bakr Al-Siddique رضى الله عنه
- To introduce the true image of the works taken up in the first half of the 20th century
- To introduce the biased approach of the author in the article.

Research Methodology

The research work will be conducted on the principles of research methodologies popular in the academia of refutation through unbiased historical research. It would also be kept in view that wherever applicable it would be the priority of the researcher to make it as easy as possible for the public as well using citations and footnotes. It would be the highest priority to refute the false allegations and clear the doubts with regard to the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه. Therefore, the study will constitute of the following attributes,

- i. The revelation of the shocking errors made in the treatment of the life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه.
- ii. Correction of the mistakes by referring to the primary sources, Sirah as well as the exegetical and historical resources.
- iii. Using scientific research methods to analyze the data.
- iv. Avoid adverse and prejudicial statements as much as possible.

- v. Introduction of the prominent works and the people in the footnotes to aid the reader.
- vi. To further aid the reader, formal citations of the works from the primary sources will be created.
- vii. Wherever applicable the science of narration would be utilized to scrutinize the narrations used by the entry's author.

Impact of the research on the society

The personality of the first caliph had always remained in the limelight due to his staunch decisions throughout his caliphate. His services to Islam and the Prophet can only truly be understood by the people who submit their will to Allah SWT. This study will clarify where the non-believers head wrong and highlight the difference between us and them. Therefore, the society understands,

- To further strengthen the love for the first adult male to accept Islam
- To establish that not everything will and can be judged under the microscope of the lab while some require spirituality.
- The dimensions for the literature had been different, readings from the west are to be taken in a context.
- The true image of the orientalist William Montgomery Watt.

Ordering of the chapters

The reader will gradually be introduced to the topic. To accomplish this, the following format will be followed,

Chapter 1: Introduction to ‘The Encyclopedia of Islam by Brill (Leiden, Holland)’

- 1.1. Introduction to The Encyclopedia of Islam
- 1.2. History and importance of The Encyclopedia of Islam in the scholarly circles of the East and the West
- 1.3. Objective and biased approach of the authors in The Encyclopedia of Islam

Chapter 2: Introduction to W. Montgomery Watt

- 2.1. Introduction to the author for the entry of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique raḍiy Allāhu ‘anhu in The Encyclopedia of Islam
- 2.2. Works, ideas and approach of the author

Chapter 3: The Orientalist’s treatment to the entry of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه

To completely analyze the entry with different scopes, it has to be divided into several different sub chapters which are as follows,

- 3.1. *The life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه before conversion.*
- 3.2. *The life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه after accepting Islam until the death of the Prophet Muhammad upon whom be peace.*
- 3.3. *The life of Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه after the death of the Prophet Muhammad upon whom be peace as the first caliph of Islam.*

Conclusion

Orientalists at several occasions have tried to mislead and distort the Islamic culture represented by events and personalities to culturally invade the true Islamic heritage. Therefore, it becomes necessary to preserve the actual doubtless history of Islam in response. This is an endeavor to spot the baseless opinions presented, rectify the doubts and wrong notions about Islam and the first caliph created by the author for the entry Abu Bakr Al – Siddique رضى الله عنه in the said entry.

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